

Investigating the effect of automatic prosodic segmentation on speech synthesis for Brazilian Portuguese

Julio Galdino¹, Rian Fernandes¹, Giovana Craveiro¹, Caroline Alves¹, Sidney Leal², Arnaldo Candido Jr.³, Flaviane Svartman¹, Sandra Aluisio¹

¹University of São Paulo (USP), ²Venturus, ³Universidade Estadual Paulista (UNESP), Brazil

Correspondence: flavianesvartman@usp.br, sandra@icmc.usp.br

Abstract

Although automatic methods of prosodic segmentation have recently been proposed, their effect on the construction of datasets for TTS training is still unknown. For the first time in Brazilian Portuguese, we investigated this type of effect on the CORAA NURC-SP Minimal Corpus dataset, consisting of $\approx 17\text{h}35\text{m}$ of spontaneous speech, which was segmented using an automatic prosodic segmenter to train a speech synthesis model. We comparatively analyzed natural speech and speech synthesized by FastSpeech2 under three segmentation conditions: manual prosodic segmentation, WhisperX automatic segmentation, and a machine learning prosodic segmentation method. The results of the acoustic prosodic analysis revealed that speech synthesized from a dataset with automatic prosodic segmentation approximates speech generated with manually segmented data, considering the representation of the F0 curve. Nevertheless, in a phonological analysis, synthetic speech exhibited a higher variability in tonal events and prosodic focus, as was also observed by Hu *et al.* (2024) for Southern British English. Furthermore, 70% of synthesized nuclear contours differed from the nuclear contours of natural speech. We attribute these issues, among other factors, to the fact that automatic segmentation does not capture systematically pauses and F0 variations, which delimit intonational units, unlike manual segmentation.

Index Terms: automatic prosodic segmentation of datasets, prosody of TTS models, Brazilian Portuguese

1. Introduction

Automatic prosodic segmentation methods have been proposed with the aim of automatically segmenting speech based on prosodic aspects such as intonation, intensity, and duration. Applied to different tasks, this technique can be useful for segmenting audios used in training TTS (Text-to-Speech) models [1, 2, 3]. However, the effect of this type of technique on the speech of these models is unclear when building datasets that have prosodic segmentation which resembles the segmentation found in natural speech. In order to verify this effect, we trained a controllable neural-based speech synthesis model (FastSpeech2) [4] with a Brazilian Portuguese (BP) audio corpus processed by an open source automatic prosodic segmenter.

Previous studies have proposed various approaches (rule-based, traditional machine learning, and deep learning) to address the challenge of automatic prosodic segmentation (see Table 1 for studies on Portuguese). For example, in [5], intonational units were predicted by combining syntactic and acoustic features using a Random Forest classifier. Applied to American English (Boston University Radio Speech Corpus), the study reported an F1 measure of 76% and an accuracy of 86.5%, using prepared speech. [6] used heuristics based on pause duration and speech rate discontinuities to detect prosodic bound-

aries in spontaneous speech from American English (Santa Barbara Corpus of Spoken American English - SBCSAE). By fine-tuning the Whisper model [7], [8] proposed a method that integrates prosodic aspects for the segmentation of spontaneous English speech. The technique segments speech by integrating prosodic and syntactic cues, and functions also as a transcription tool. It achieved 96% accuracy and 87% F1 measure for American English (SBCSAE) and 93% accuracy and 73% F1 measure for British English (Intonational Variation in English (IViE) corpus).

For European Portuguese, [9] detected pauses from spectrograms and a convolutional neural network, using prepared speech. The technique achieved 95.6% accuracy and works for any language, but there is only an indication of limits based on pauses, which may be subject to acoustic biases. For BP, there is the study by [10], which presented a Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) classifier applied to spontaneous speech. Extracting 111 phonetic-acoustic features from the corpora, the method included the speech rate, duration, fundamental frequency, and pauses. The best results showed an accuracy measure of 80.8% for terminal units and 75.6% for non-terminal units, with an overall average of 78.2%. Also for spontaneous BP, there is the method by [11], which detected prosodic boundaries using the forced phonetic aligner UFPAlign [12] and the same heuristics as [6]. The results indicated an F1 measure of 31%, using a 5-hour excerpt from the NURC-SP Minimal Corpus (MC), which reflects the linguistic variety of BP in São Paulo. In [13], inspired by the work of [14], the authors used nine acoustic-prosodic features to train a Random Forest classifier, and reported a F1 measure of 77% and an accuracy of 97% in the Mupe-Diversidades corpus (speech from 17 Brazilian states).

In this work, we use the method described in [13], since it is a recent method for BP, it achieved a good F1 score, and it used spontaneous BP data similar to those used in this work. Our work seeks to answer the following research question: does automatic prosodic segmentation contribute to speech synthesis prosodic quality in the same way as manual segmentation? What is the observed effect? Our work aligns with the study by [15], in terms of experimental protocol, as we also examine the influence of manual and automatic annotations of prosodic boundaries in BP on the quality of synthesized speech. We compare the results by [15] on the segmentation of WhisperX [16] and on human prosodic segmentation performed at NURC-SP MC to contrast with our results. Our study is also closely related to the work of [17], which evaluates whether OpenAI's TTS model can convey information status using intonation like humans, although our work uses the FastSpeech 2 TTS model, widely used in the field of speech architectures [18, 19], as it is a model that controls energy, pitch, and duration.

Table 1: Summary of prosodic segmentation research on prepared and spontaneous speech

Source	Language	Corpus	F1 Score/Accuracy	Is Code Available ?	Speech
Hoi et al. (2022)	PT-PT	RTP - https://www.rtp.pt/ (~33hs)	—/95.6%	No	Prepared
Raso et al. (2020)	PT-BR	C-Oral Brasil I and C-Oral Brasil II (~17min)	—/78.2%	No	Spontaneous
Craveiro et al. (2024)	PT-BR	Part of the NURC-SP MC (~5hrs)	31%/—	Open Code	Spontaneous
Craveiro et al. (2025)	PT-BR	MuPe-Diversidades (2h30min)	77%/97%	Open Code	Spontaneous
Our Work	PT-BR	NURC-SP MC (14h51min)	61%/93%	Open Code https://github.com/nllc-nlp/ProsSegue	Spontaneous

2. Experimental Setup

2.1. NURC-SP MC

We used data from the NURC-SP MC [20], since it is prosodically segmented by human annotators. The dataset is a resource in spontaneous BP, specifically from the São Paulo variety. In total, it consists of 21 audio files (.wav, 2 channels, 16 bits, 48 kHz), totaling 17h35min19s, with six formal utterances (EF), for instance, lectures and conference talks, six dialogues between two informants (D2), and nine dialogues between informant and interviewer (DID); the recordings were primarily conducted face-to-face. There are text files aligned with the speech (.textgrid, UTF-8) annotated in the Praat software [21]. The human annotators based their work on the theory of [22], which considers the prosodic segmentation of speech into non-terminal breaks (NTB) and terminal breaks (TB). Originally recorded on reel-to-reel tape in the 1970s, the dataset was later digitized and is available in the Portulan Clarin repository under the CC BY-NC-ND 4.0 license. Information about the informants and the quality of each inquiry can be found in the metadata in [20].

2.2. Automatic prosodic boundary segmentation approach

The method chosen for the segmentation was reported in [13]. It covers solely TBs and considers 9 features at the syllable level, with the following order of importance: pause duration, energy range, difference between maximum and average energy, f0 range, nucleus vowel duration, difference between maximum and average f0, difference between minimum and average f0, difference between minimum and average energy, and difference between average f0 of the syllable and average f0 of the utterance (f0_avgutt_diff). We made three changes to the original approach, since it is an open source code.

The first change concerns the version of UFPALIGN, the forced aligner used in [13]. Since their research, UFPALIGN was updated by the authors, maintaining solely a version based on m2maligner (<https://github.com/letter-to-phoneme/m2m-aligner>), which was used in [13] exclusively to process problematic audios. Thus, we used such version to process NURC-SP MC. The second change concerns the interviewers’ speech, which they filtered. Even though their intent was to preserve the balance across speaker profile (the interviewees were carefully selected according to gender, age, and region of birth, while the interviewers were not controlled in such manner), they also removed several questions from the dataset since those were present in the speech of the interviewers. Thus, we retrained their Random Forest model with the same parameters that they used, but using the entire MuPe-Diversidades corpus, without filtering any speech. The third change concerns the features used. While they included a feature that required a previous annotation of prosodic boundaries (f0_avgutt_diff), limiting the method’s usability, we chose to exclude f0_avgutt_diff and use only 8 features when retraining their model, a suggestion they made. We tested our model’s performance (the one with the changes) by separating training and test sets of MuPe-

Diversidades with the same methodology they used and by using their code to measure results. We obtained the same value of F1-macro (77%) that they reported. Once we had the model ready, the next phase was to prosodically segment the corpus NURC-SP MC that we intend to evaluate here.

2.3. NURC-SP MC segmentation

For automatic prosodic segmentation, we used 19 inquiries from NURC-SP MC. Inquiry D2.62 was discarded due to the high noise rate described in the metadata. Inquiry DID.234 was processed by the automatic segmenter for error analysis of the segmentation task and was reserved for the TTS model testing phase and analyses (see Section 3). In the **pre-processing stage**, the data was converted to 16 kHz, in monophonic signal, remaining in .wav format. The phonetic aligner used by [13] process short audio, so the files were manually divided into segments lasting ≈ 20 minutes. For some audios, the limitations of the aligner led to even smaller cuts, between 5 to 10 minutes. The cuts were made manually in order to avoid abrupt interruptions in speech, such as divisions in words or inappropriate segmentations. The audio transcripts were normalized based on the script used in [13], which converted the textgrid into a .txt file with words separated by a single space, without punctuation marks and without overlaps. In the **processing stage** of the model, the phonetic aligner with UFPALIGN [12] marks the start and end times of each phoneme, syllable, and word in the audio files. Then, prosodic information was extracted using the Parselmouth library (<https://github.com/YannickJadoul/Parselmouth>). Finally, the end result is a textgrid with different intervals, prosodically segmented using the Random Forest classifier.

2.4. TTS training

For a fair comparison, we followed the same setup from [15] and trained the FastSpeech2 (FS2) model with the new segmented dataset (NURC-SP MC). FastSpeech2 is a model that estimates and keeps track of duration, pitch, and energy during training and inference. More details are available in the website <https://nllc-nlp.github.io/entoa-tts-prossegue>.

3. Results

3.1. Phonetic prosodic analysis

We compared our sample of 30 utterances synthesized by FS2, trained with data processed by the automatic prosodic segmenter (APS), similarly to the data from the three groups analyzed in [15]: (i) 30 declarative utterances from speaker L1-234 of NURC-SP MC [Natural Speech]; (ii) 30 utterances from FS2 [Manual Segmentation (MS) - NURC-SP MC]; and (iii) 30 utterances from FS2 [Automatic Segmentation (AS) - WhisperX]. In Praat [21], we considered the natural speech annotations indicated by [15], labeling four points of fundamental frequency (F0). The points mark: 1. the first syllable of the utterance (onset); 2. a point before the higher F0 peak of BP declaratives

(prnuc); 3. a point associated with the higher F0 peak of declarative utterances in BP (nuc); and 4. the lowest movement of the final F0 fall (psnuc). We extracted the maximum F0 value using the AnalyseTier script [23] and calculated the average. We converted the F0 values into semitones relative to 100 Hz, as this is a way of normalizing different speech recordings [24], such as natural and synthesized speech. We consider how the representation of the F0 curve varies, which allows us to verify consecutive changes in the points. To do this, one possible analysis is to calculate the deviation from the series mean (Figure 1).

Visually, speech synthesized by FS2-APS shows variations between points in a similar way to FS2-MS speech. We use natural speech as a reference to calculate successive differences between points (More details at: <https://nilc-nlp.github.io/entoatts-prossegue>) (Figure 2). For the onset-prnuc transition, FS2-APS shows a drop, deviating -0.65 semitones from natural speech, while FS2-MS also shows a drop (-1.51), although more pronounced. FS2-AS reveals behavior closer to the reference speech in this downward transition, but it fails in the following transition, which may indicate that this variation exists more by numerical chance than exactly because of prosodic coherence. Between prnuc - nuc, there is an increase in the FS2-MS and FS2-APS, following the direction of the higher F0 peak of the BP declarative sentences although these amplitudes are much smaller. The speech synthesized by FS2-APS and FS2-MS has similar behaviors. However, none of the three FS2 groups managed to precisely level the representation of the F0 contour of human speech, producing unnatural intonations.

Figure 1: Deviation from the mean F0 curve

3.2. Phonological prosodic analysis

Following the theoretical framework of Autosegmental-Metric Intonational Phonology [25], integrated with the Prosodic Phonology [26], we worked in Praat software with three layers of annotation: (1) “Tones,” a layer in which we annotated the nuclear contour, according to the P.ToBI prosodic annotation system [27, 28], (2) “Segmentation,” a layer in which the corresponding excerpts were manually transcribed and segmented into words, and (3) “BI,” a layer containing the boundaries of prosodic domains (in which we only noted the boundary of the intonational phrase, with “4”). For natural speech files, in approximately 77% of the data, we found, with regard to the nuclear contour of declarative utterances, what [29] had already attested in their data: a descending final contour. However, synthesized speech of the FS2-APS (Table 2) presents a diversity of final nuclear contours, causing the absence of a pattern for the production of these contours.

Figure 2: Successive difference between F0 points
Table 2: Nuclear Contours of declarative utterances in Synthesized Speech

Nuclear Contour	Ocurrences (n=30)
(L+)H* H%	6
L* L%	5
H+L* L%	5
H*+L L%	4
L*+H H%	4
(L+)H* L%	3
(L+)H* !H%	3

Furthermore, the synthesized audio exhibited focus on different parts of the utterance, which is not expected in a neutral context. This supports the hypothesis of [17], who investigated utterances containing only two words and already identified variability in focus production: “(...) for sentences with more complex structures the variability in focus location may well increase.”

Figure 3: Natural speech phonological analysis

In natural speech utterance (Figure 3), the speaker raises the pitch on the prosodic word “sei” (I know), the head of the first intonational phrase, which is expected. In synthesized speech (Figure 4), we notice an emphasis on “eu” (I), an unexpected location for a rise in pitch; furthermore, we see in “preparação” (preparation) the accentuation of the first syllable, rather than the last, which is not predicted by BP grammar.

Figure 4: Synthesized speech phonological analysis

3.3. Error analysis of automatic prosodic segmentation

In the last line of Table 1, we show the results of F1 score and accuracy of the automatic segmentation method of [13] applied to NURC-SP MC. The F1 score obtained showed a performance drop of 16%, compared to the original method, and configures the second lowest F1 reported considering all the approaches mentioned in Table 1. Using this segmenter, we obtained a segmentation as illustrated in Figure 5, referring to a speech excerpt from the DID-234 inquiry belonging to the NURC-SP MC. When we compare the segmentation generated by the automatic segmenter (first layer of Praat) with the result of manual segmentation (second layer of Praat) for the same speech segment, we observe limitations of the automatic model, especially with regard to the accurate identification of: (1) silent pauses (segments without phonation), (2) intonational contours that signal the limits of TB and NTB boundaries of utterances, and (3) changes in tessitura.

Figure 5: Automatic segmentation excerpt from DID-234

Automatic segmentation identifies only one initial boundary and one final boundary for the entire utterance, treating it as a single intonational unit (Figure 5). In contrast, manual segmentation identifies two distinct TBs, corresponding to two intonational groups: “eu tenho ido bastante” (I’ve been going a lot) and “prefiro ir a teatro do que a cinema” (I prefer going to the theater rather than the movies). These segmentations differ because human annotation seems to be more sensitive to the combination of prosodic cues present in the acoustic signal. Among these cues, the drop in F0 curve at the end of the first segment (marked by the circle in the figure) stands out, indicating a melodic movement typical of the conclusion of the utterance and, therefore, compatible with the marking of a TB of an intonational unit. In addition, there is a clear change in tessitura between the two segments, evidenced by the horizontal lines positioned above the F0 curve: the first segment is produced in a lower tessitura, while the second begins in a higher and relatively stable tessitura. Added to this evidence is the presence of a long silent pause, visible in the spectrogram, which reinforces the interpretation that the utterance is composed of two distinct TBs.

4. Discussions and Conclusion

This study compared the prosody of speech synthesized by FS2 under three speech segmentation conditions. The results of the phonetic prosodic analysis showed that FS2-APS had a similar effect to FS2-MS. We understand that FS2 with segmentation produced automatically by WhisperX reveals less prosodic variation, which may mean more monotonous synthesized speech. Thus, our study contributes to the understanding of factors that may have an effect on the intonational elements of speech generated by TTS models. Conventional segmentation may explain why FS2 performed worse than the other two conditions. WhisperX does not take into account the structure of speech discourse, which can lead to abrupt cuts in the middle of a sen-

tence, for example. We understand that this can lead to the loss of prosodic information, making the model less likely to learn from the data. On the other hand, FS2-APS and FS2-MS learn segments based on intonational units, leading to a better representation of the prosody of declarative sentences in BP. Another possible hypothesis for the poor performance of FS2-AS is the fact that this WhisperX segmentation was not manually reviewed, which may be an interesting factor to analyze in future work. At the same time, we understand that our study is an initial step toward investigating segmentation, as there are methodological limitations. Even so, none of the three conditions achieved the variation of natural speech, especially in the final F0 drop, where natural speech has a greater dimension than the speech of the three FS2 groups. Our hypothesis is that the number of hours in NURC-SP MC implies the model’s limited ability to generalize prosody, causing F0 variations to not be well captured.

In addition, it is a dataset that was initially recorded with reel-to-reel tape quality in the 1970s, which may perhaps influence the final result of the synthesis. For the model to achieve efficient optimization, it was necessary to use an additional dataset, CML-TTS, to increase the number of hours and assist in vocabulary acquisition. In addition, model training is a process that can take time, which led us to use only one model in this study. FS2 also has specific characteristics, such as preventing the generation of speech from a speaker outside the training set. Thus, future research may probe the influence of other factors that may have an effect on the prosody of synthesized speech, such as the impact of quality, number of hours, dataset merging, and the performance of TTS models from other approaches [18]. Finally, the results on errors in automatic prosodic segmenter revealed that improvements are necessary. This gap can be filled by investigating the effect of an approach based on deep learning, following the work of [8], or even an intermediate approach that combines linguistic knowledge with the data learning capabilities of machine learning methods.

By comparing different dataset segmentation conditions, this study showed that speech synthesized with automatic prosodic segmentation has an effect close to that of speech synthesized from manual prosodic segmentation. However, none of the synthesized speech precisely matched the oscillations of natural speech, as attested by phonological analysis, due to the difference in the attribution of tonal events, nuclear contours, and focus. Our results show that it is important to consider prosodic information when building datasets, but we emphasize that they reveal evidence in the speech of a single TTS model, using a small dataset, and automatically segmenting TBs.

5. Acknowledgments

This work was carried out at the Center for Artificial Intelligence (C4AI-USP), with support by the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP grant #2019/07665-4) and by the IBM Corporation. This project was also supported by the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, with resources of Law No. 8.248, of October 23, 1991, within the scope of PPI-SOFTEX, coordinated by Softex and published Residence in TIC 13, DOU 01245.010222/2022-44. We thank the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel - Brazil (CAPES) for the grant 88887.920395/2023-00, through the Academic Excellence Program (PROEX), and National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq) for the grant 304460/2024-9. We thank Prof. Miguel Oliveira Jr. for his valuable suggestions regarding the phonetic prosodic analysis.

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